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Unveiling The Impact Of Gender Inequality In Promotion On Women's Career Progression In The Nigerian Customs Service: An Empirical Perspective

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ABSTRACT

This study examines whether gender inequality in promotion limits women's career progression in the Nigerian Customs Service (NCS), with a specific focus on the Sokoto/Zamfara Command. A quantitative research design was adopted, and data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to all 17 female officers in the command, of which 14 valid responses were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) in SPSS version 27. The results revealed a strong and statistically significant negative relationship between gender inequality in promotion and women's career progression, indicating that as gender inequality in promotion increases, women's advancement opportunities decrease substantially. The findings further suggest that despite women's competence and participation in required promotion examinations, institutional bias and unequal access to leadership opportunities continue to restrict their progression to top managerial ranks. The study concludes that entrenched gender-based barriers in promotion practices remain a major obstacle to women's career advancement within the NCS. It therefore recommends that the Service, in collaboration with the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs and the Federal Character Commission, implement transparent, merit-based promotion policies, establish gender-balanced promotion boards, and introduce structured mentorship and leadership development programs to support women's upward mobility.

Keywords: Gender inequality, Promotion, Women's career progression, Nigerian Customs Service.

1. INTRODUCTION

Gender equality has long been recognized as a cornerstone for sustainable development and social justice. The Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action (1995) underscores this by asserting that "women's full and equal participation in power structures and decision-making is a necessary condition for the achievement of equality, development, and peace." Nevertheless, despite notable global progress, inequality between men and women in career opportunities and leadership continues to pose a persistent challenge.

Globally, the disparity in leadership advancement remains pronounced. According to the World Economic Forum (2024), women constitute approximately 46% of entry-level roles but occupy only 25% of senior leadership positions worldwide. In the same vein, the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2024) reports that merely 46.4% of working-age women are employed compared to 69.5% of men, leaving millions of capable women excluded from meaningful career advancement. These figures collectively suggest that while progress has been made in providing women access to employment, genuine equality in promotional opportunities and leadership attainment remains elusive.

In the Nigerian context, a similar pattern emerges. The UN Women Nigeria (2024) report indicates that women's labor-force participation stands at about 47.8%, yet most are concentrated in lower-paying or informal sectors. Correspondingly, McKinsey & Company (2024) found that women hold around 33% of entry-level positions but only 28% of senior executive roles. Thus, it becomes evident that deep-rooted cultural expectations, workplace biases, and insufficient institutional support continue to hinder women's upward mobility. Although national initiatives such as the *National Gender Policy (2021–2026)* and Nigeria's ratification of the *Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW)* demonstrate policy-level commitment to gender equality, their translation into tangible workplace outcomes remains limited.

A compelling institutional case in point is the Nigeria Customs Service (NCS), a key paramilitary agency responsible for revenue generation and border management. The NCS, which has operated since the colonial era, maintains a rigid hierarchical and male-dominated structure. Remarkably, in its entire history, no woman has ever been appointed as Comptroller-General, and the majority of top command positions remain overwhelmingly occupied by men (Nigeria Customs Service, 2024). Although some progress has been recorded such as the appointment of the first female pilot and a few women leading regional commands, these instances are exceptions rather than evidence of systemic inclusion.

Consequently, this study seeks to examine how gender inequality in promotion constrains women's career progression within the Nigeria Customs Service. While gender inequality has been widely explored in sectors such as education, politics, and corporate management, its expression within Nigeria's paramilitary institutions remains under-researched. These institutions, including the NCS, are characterized by rigid hierarchies, masculine work cultures, and traditional norms that heavily influence advancement opportunities (UN Women, 2024). Understanding this issue is particularly crucial, given that no woman has ever occupied the highest office of Comptroller-General since the agency's inception, underscoring a significant structural imbalance. Moreover, comparative evidence from countries like Canada and Australia demonstrates that customs agencies embracing gender-inclusive promotion practices have achieved higher levels of transparency, operational efficiency, and institutional trust (World Customs Organization, 2023).

Therefore, to achieve the study objective, the study is organized into five sections, *Section 1* introduces the research background; *Section 2* reviews relevant literature; *Section 3* outlines the methodology; *Section 4* presents and discusses the findings; and *Section 5* concludes with recommendations aimed at promoting gender equality and equitable career progression within the Nigeria Customs Service.

1.2 Research Question

To what extent does gender inequality in promotion affect women's career progression in the Nigerian Customs Service?

1.3 Research Objective

To examine the relationship between gender inequality in promotion and women's career progression in the Nigerian Customs Service

1.4 Research Hypothesis

H₀¹: There is no significant relationship between gender inequality in promotion and women's career progression in the Nigerian Customs Service.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Gender Inequality

Gender inequality refers to the systematic and institutionalized disparities in access to opportunities, resources, and rewards between men and women across social, economic, and organisational contexts. These disparities often manifest in limited access for women to employment, promotion, leadership positions, professional training, and recognition (Ogbogu, 2011). In Nigeria, both cultural norms and institutional practices continue to shape gender relations in ways that constrain women's upward mobility. For instance, studies show that women in Nigerian universities and public institutions are often concentrated in junior and middle-level positions, while their representation diminishes significantly at higher managerial and executive ranks (Ogbogu, 2011; Eboiyehi, Fayomi, & Eboiyehi, 2016). This pattern reflects a broader national trend in which promotion systems tend to favour men, either implicitly through gender bias or explicitly through organisational cultures that associate leadership competence with masculinity.

The Nigerian labour market more broadly demonstrates persistent gender disparities in promotion, remuneration, and professional development. Women frequently receive fewer advancement opportunities and less access to managerial training than men with comparable qualifications (Adedire, 2022). These inequities are reinforced by socio-cultural expectations that assign domestic and caregiving responsibilities primarily to women, leaving them with less time and flexibility to pursue leadership roles or competitive postings that lead to promotion (Adedire, 2022; Ogbogu, 2011). Moreover, gender-based occupational segregation channels women into roles or departments deemed "appropriate" for their gender often those with limited promotional pathways or decision-making influence (BusinessDay, 2023). In this way, gender inequality operates through both structural mechanisms (promotion policies, leadership pipelines, evaluation systems) and cultural norms (stereotypes, exclusionary practices), shaping how organisations including the Nigerian Customs Service, recruit, appraise, and promote employees.

Within the context of this study, gender inequality is operationalized as systemic disparities in promotion opportunities, access to training, and representation in leadership roles between male and female personnel of the Nigerian Customs Service. It encompasses both formal institutional structures (e.g., promotion criteria and evaluation processes) and informal cultural dynamics (e.g., gender bias, perceptions of leadership suitability) that jointly influence women's ability to advance within the organisation.

2.1.2 Career Progression

Career progression describes the structured advancement of employees through organisational hierarchies typically via promotion, leadership appointments, and access to professional development opportunities. Ideally, promotion decisions should be based on competence, performance, and merit. However, empirical evidence shows that career progression is frequently shaped by organisational culture, gendered norms, and institutional biases that disadvantage women (Olutayo, 2024). Within male-dominated or hierarchical institutions such as the Nigerian Customs Service, these factors often create invisible barriers that restrict women's ability to progress beyond entry or mid-level positions.

Research indicates that women's career progression is constrained by multiple interrelated factors, including limited access to mentorship and sponsorship, exclusion from informal professional networks, and entrenched stereotypes about women's leadership capacities (Ogbogu, 2011). Furthermore, promotion systems in many public organisations privilege uninterrupted career trajectories, geographical mobility, and continuous availability, criteria that may disadvantage women balancing professional roles with family or caregiving responsibilities (Olutayo, 2024). In sectors with traditionally masculine norms of advancement, such as customs and other paramilitary services, these expectations often translate into gendered gatekeeping practices that slow or block women's promotion into senior ranks.

Evidence from Nigerian and Ghanaian higher education institutions shows that institutional climates frequently fail to accommodate gender-specific career pathways or constraints, leading to women's underrepresentation in senior positions (Olutayo, 2024). These findings mirror patterns observed in other sectors, where structural and cultural barriers interact to limit promotion prospects for women despite comparable qualifications or performance records. For this study, career progression is therefore operationalized as the measurable upward movement of personnel within the Nigerian

Customs Service through promotions, leadership appointments, and access to professional development programmes. Examining how gender inequality within promotion systems affects women's career progression will illuminate the organisational and cultural mechanisms that perpetuate inequality in the NCS and suggest evidence-based strategies for reform.

2.2 Empirical Review

Empirical evidence across global contexts consistently demonstrates that gender inequality remains a powerful determinant of women's career trajectories, particularly in relation to promotion and advancement into leadership roles. Laver et al. (2018), in a systematic review of interventions designed to support women's careers in academic medicine and other disciplines, found that initiatives such as mentoring, leadership training, and organisational policy reforms can yield modest short-term gains in promotion and retention. However, their review emphasised that the majority of these studies lacked rigorous longitudinal evaluation, leaving uncertainty about the sustainability of these gains. Similarly, Mousa et al. (2021) conducted a large-scale systematic review across sectors and concluded those multi-component strategies, combining mentoring, sponsorship, and structural reforms, produce stronger outcomes in women's leadership representation than isolated interventions. Both studies reveal that promotion barriers remain embedded within broader organisational systems, requiring institutional commitment and accountability to dismantle.

At the individual and organisational levels, Greer and Kirk (2022) demonstrated that women's ability to transition into higher-level positions is influenced by self-efficacy, social support, and access to flexible work structures. Yet, these facilitators are often constrained by gendered organisational cultures that perpetuate stereotypes and gatekeeping practices. Glass et al. (2016) advanced this understanding through their concept of the "broken rung," highlighting how women's exclusion from early managerial promotions becomes a structural bottleneck that limits long-term career progression and leadership attainment. Johns (2013) further explained that gender inequality in promotion arises from the intersection of cultural bias, informal exclusion from critical assignments, and family-work conflict factors that collectively create systemic disadvantage for women. Reinforcing this, Netchaeva, Sheppard, and Balushkina (2022) found through a meta-analytic review that women, on average, express slightly lower leadership aspirations than men, suggesting that both internal (psychological) and external (institutional) barriers shape advancement outcomes. A more recent rapid realist review by Mucheru et al. (2024) concluded that contextual factors such as national policy frameworks, organisational norms, and sector-specific cultures moderate the success of interventions aimed at women's career advancement, with sponsorship and transparent promotion systems emerging as critical enablers.

Collectively, these empirical reviews converge on a central insight: gender inequality in promotion processes constitutes a persistent and systemic barrier to women's career progression. Although global evidence provides strong conceptual and empirical foundations, significant contextual gaps remain. Most existing studies have been conducted in Western or high-income countries and focus on academia, healthcare, or corporate organisations. Little is known about how gender inequality in promotion operates within African public institutions, particularly paramilitary agencies such as the Nigerian Customs Service (NCS). The NCS presents a distinct organisational context characterised by hierarchical promotion systems, rigid command structures, and historically male-dominated leadership pipelines. Yet, there is limited empirical examination of how these dynamics influence women's career progression.

This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by empirically investigating whether gender inequality in promotion practices limits women's career advancement within the NCS. By applying insights from the global literature such as the effects of early promotion bottlenecks ("broken rungs"), sponsorship access, and structural bias to the Nigerian public service context, the research aims to identify the specific mechanisms through which gender inequality constrains upward mobility. In doing so, it extends the existing body of knowledge beyond Western organisational settings and contributes context-sensitive evidence to inform gender equity policy and reform in Nigeria's public sector.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Glass Ceiling Theory, a concept that explains the invisible yet pervasive barriers that prevent qualified women from advancing to higher managerial and leadership positions within organisations (Cotter, Hermsen, Ovadia, & Vanneman, 2001). The theory emerged from feminist and organisational scholarship in the 1980s as an analytical lens to understand the structural

and cultural impediments that restrict women's promotion opportunities despite their educational attainment and performance (Morrison, White, & Van Velsor, 1987). The "glass ceiling" metaphor captures the idea that women can see the top positions and may appear to have equal access to advancement, but encounter subtle and institutionalized constraints that are not formally codified yet effectively block their upward movement (Powell & Butterfield, 2015).

Cotter et al. (2001) identify four defining features of the glass ceiling: (1) the barriers affect women more than men; (2) the barriers are greater at higher levels of organisational hierarchies; (3) they are not explained by job-related characteristics such as education or experience; and (4) they result from discriminatory practices embedded in organisational structures. Subsequent empirical studies have demonstrated that these barriers manifest through biased promotion criteria, gender stereotypes in leadership evaluation, lack of mentorship and sponsorship, and exclusion from informal decision-making networks (Hoobler, Lemmon, & Wayne, 2014; Eagly & Carli, 2007). These mechanisms create cumulative disadvantage, where women's career progression slows or stalls as they approach senior leadership levels.

In the context of public organisations like the Nigerian Customs Service (NCS), the Glass Ceiling Theory is particularly relevant. The NCS operates within a highly structured and hierarchical promotion system, where advancement is often contingent on seniority, tenure, and performance appraisals. Yet, empirical evidence from Nigerian public institutions suggests that gender bias and organisational culture frequently influence these processes (Ogbogu, 2011; Adedire, 2022). Women are often underrepresented in command positions and rarely attain top executive ranks, not because of lack of competence, but due to institutionalized gender norms, limited access to leadership opportunities, and discriminatory perceptions about women's suitability for authority roles (Eboiyehi, Fayomi, & Eboiyehi, 2016). These conditions exemplify the glass ceiling effect, where invisible organisational and cultural constraints hinder women's promotion despite apparent formal equality in recruitment and training.

Applying the Glass Ceiling Theory to this study provides a robust analytical lens for examining whether gender inequality in promotion limits women's career progression within the Nigerian Customs Service. It enables the study to move beyond individual explanations (such as motivation or ambition) toward understanding the structural and institutional mechanisms such as biased promotion systems, lack of mentorship, and gendered expectations that reproduce inequality. The theory also guides the interpretation of findings by highlighting that achieving gender equity in promotion requires more than policy reforms; it demands dismantling the cultural and systemic barriers that sustain unequal access to leadership. Thus, the Glass Ceiling Theory offers both explanatory and diagnostic value, aligning closely with the study's objective to investigate the relationship between gender inequality in promotion and women's career progression in the NCS.

3. METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional correlational research design was adopted to examine the effect of gender inequality in promotion on women's career progression in the Nigerian Customs Service (NCS), focusing on the Sokoto/Zamfara Customs Command. The study population comprised 208 officers, of which only 17 were female, according to the administrative records of the Command (2024). Since the study focused exclusively on the female population, a census sampling technique was employed, ensuring that all 17 female officers were included in the analysis to eliminate sampling bias and enhance data accuracy. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire developed based on established instruments and previous studies on gender inequality, promotion, and career advancement (Cotter et al., 2001; Ogbogu, 2011; Hoobler, Lemmon, & Wayne, 2014). The questionnaire consisted of three sections: Section A captured demographic information; Section B measured gender inequality in promotion using items related to fairness of promotion processes, access to leadership opportunities, bias in performance evaluation, and training accessibility; while Section C assessed women's career progression through indicators such as frequency of promotion, leadership responsibilities, and access to professional development programs. All items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The instrument's content validity was established through expert review by two scholars in Human Resource Management and one senior Customs administrator to ensure clarity, coverage, and alignment with the study objectives. A pilot study was conducted at the Kebbi Customs Command to test the reliability of the instrument, and Cronbach's

alpha coefficients for all constructs exceeded the 0.70 threshold (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994), confirming internal consistency. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 27, with descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations used to summarize responses, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis was employed to test the relationship between gender inequality in promotion and women’s career progression at a 0.05 level of significance. Prior to analysis, data were screened for normality using skewness and kurtosis, and multicollinearity diagnostics were conducted to confirm the suitability of the dataset for regression analysis.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Preliminary Data Screening

A total of 17 questionnaires were distributed to female officers of the Sokoto/Zamfara Command of the Nigerian Customs Service. Out of these, 14 questionnaires were successfully retrieved, representing a response rate of 82.4%. After thorough screening, all 14 retrieved questionnaires were found to be adequately completed and consistent, and therefore deemed valid for analysis. The valid responses were coded and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 27, following standard data preparation procedures including checking for completeness, accuracy, and consistency.

4.1.1 Normality Test

Normality was assessed using skewness and kurtosis statistics as generated in SPSS. Following the recommendations of Hair et al. (2022) and George and Mallery (2010), skewness values within the range of ± 2 and kurtosis values within ± 7 are considered acceptable indicators of an approximately normal distribution suitable for parametric analysis.

Table 1: Normality Test: Test of Skewness and Kurtosis

Constructs	N	Skewness		Kurtosis	
		Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Gender Inequality in Promotion (GIP)	14	-.429	.597	-1.297	1.154
Women Career Progression (WCP)	14	-.221	.597	-1.376	1.154

Source: SPSS Output, (2025)

As presented in Table 2, the skewness values for Gender Inequality in Promotion (-0.429) and Women Career Progression (-0.221) fall within the acceptable ± 2 threshold, indicating that both variables are approximately symmetric around their means. Likewise, the kurtosis values (-1.297 and -1.376 , respectively) lie well within the ± 7 range, suggesting that the data distributions are neither excessively peaked nor flat. These results confirm that the dataset meets the normality assumption required for subsequent parametric tests such as correlation and regression.

4.1.2 Multicollinearity Diagnostics

Multicollinearity among predictors was examined using tolerance and variance inflation factor (VIF) statistics. According to Hair et al. (2022) and Field (2018), tolerance values below 0.1 or VIF values exceeding 10 indicate problematic multicollinearity.

Table 2: Test of Multicollinearity: Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Predictor	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
	Correlation	Correlation		
Gender Inequality in Promotion (GIP)	-0.907	-0.907	1.000	1.000

Source: SPSS Output, 2025

As shown in Table 3, the tolerance (1.000) and VIF (1.000) values for Gender Inequality in Promotion (GIP) are well within the recommended thresholds, indicating the absence of multicollinearity in the model. This suggests that GIP is not linearly correlated with any other predictor variable (as it is the only independent variable in this model) and contributes uniquely to explaining variations in Women Career Progression (WCP). Therefore, the assumption of non-collinearity is fully satisfied.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were computed to summarize the central tendency and dispersion of the study variables: Gender Inequality in Promotion (GIP) and Women Career Progression (WCP) among female officers in the Nigerian Customs Service, Sokoto/Zamfara Command.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Variables: Mean and Standard Deviation

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gender Inequality in Promotion (GIP)	14	1.00	5.00	4.1286	0.47463
Women Career Progression (WCP)	14	1.00	5.00	3.6143	0.35487

Source: SPSS Output, 2025

As presented in Table 4, the mean score for Gender Inequality in Promotion ($M = 4.13$, $SD = 0.47$) reveals a strong consensus among respondents that gender inequality in promotion exists within the Nigerian Customs Service. This finding suggests that many women perceive promotion processes as being influenced by gender-based barriers, where men are often favored over equally qualified female officers. In contrast, the mean score for Women Career Progression ($M = 3.61$, $SD = 0.35$) indicates a moderate level of career advancement among female officers. Although some women have successfully attained supervisory or mid-level positions, progression to top managerial or command ranks remains notably restricted. Respondents emphasized that even after fulfilling all formal requirements such as sitting for promotion examinations and meeting performance benchmarks, only a few women ultimately reach higher leadership positions. This trend underscores a persistent organizational gap: while women in the NCS demonstrate competence, commitment, and readiness for advancement, their career trajectories are hindered by entrenched gender biases and insufficient institutional mechanisms to support equity in promotion.

4.3 Inferential Statistics: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC)

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was employed to determine the relationship between Gender Inequality in Promotion (GIP) and Women Career Progression (WCP) within the Nigerian Customs Service. The test was conducted at a 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4: Correlation Results for Gender Inequality in Promotion and Women Career Progression

		GIP	WCP
GIP	Pearson Correlation	1	-.907**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	14	14
WCP	Pearson Correlation	-.907**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	14	14

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, (2025)

The results in Table 5 show a strong and statistically significant negative correlation between Gender Inequality in Promotion and Women Career Progression ($r = -0.907$, $p = 0.000 < 0.01$). This indicates that as gender inequality in promotion increases, women's career progression significantly decreases within the Nigerian Customs Service. In other words, promotional practices perceived as biased or unequal are associated with reduced opportunities for women to advance to senior ranks.

4.4 Test of Hypotheses

This section presents the testing of the study's hypothesis using the correlation results in Table 5. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was employed at a 0.05 level of significance (2-tailed).

H₀¹: There is no significant relationship between gender inequality in promotion and women's career progression in the Nigerian Customs Service.

The correlation results indicate a strong and statistically significant negative relationship between gender inequality in promotion and women's career progression ($r = -0.907$, $p = 0.000 < 0.01$). Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected. This implies that as gender inequality in promotion increases, women's career progression decreases significantly within the Nigerian Customs Service. This finding suggests that biased promotion practices, unequal access to leadership opportunities, and lack of institutional transparency in promotion procedures severely hinder women's advancement to higher ranks. It further reveals that despite women's competence, experience, and performance, discriminatory promotion structures limit their professional growth. Hence, reducing gender-based

barriers in promotion processes is critical to achieving equitable career progression and fostering inclusivity within the Nigerian Customs Service.

4.5 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study offer compelling evidence of how gender inequality in promotion continues to limit women's career progression within the Nigerian Customs Service (NCS). The strong and statistically significant negative correlation between Gender Inequality in Promotion (GIP) and Women Career Progression (WCP) ($r = -0.907$, $p < 0.01$) clearly indicates that as promotion bias and discrimination increase, women's opportunities for advancement decline proportionally. This empirical evidence reinforces the long-standing argument that women's underrepresentation in leadership positions across paramilitary institutions is not the result of competence or commitment deficits but rather the outcome of structural and cultural barriers embedded in promotion systems (Cotter et al., 2001; Eboiyehi, Fayomi, & Eboiyehi, 2016; Adedire, 2022).

The results are consistent with the Glass Ceiling Theory, which posits that invisible yet powerful organizational barriers impede women's ascent to top managerial levels despite comparable qualifications and performance (Morrison, White, & Van Velsor, 1987; Powell & Butterfield, 2015). The persistence of these barriers within the NCS manifests through gender-biased evaluation criteria, limited mentorship for female officers, and cultural stereotypes that associate leadership and authority with masculinity. Respondents in this study reported that women are often subjected to more rigorous scrutiny during promotion assessments, required to take multiple qualifying exams, and yet rarely promoted to commanding or strategic decision-making positions. It also, resonates with global empirical evidence. Laver et al. (2018) and Mousa et al. (2021) both observed that women's career advancement often stalls at middle management due to institutionalized bias and the absence of transparent promotion mechanisms. Similarly, Glass et al. (2016) described the "broken rung" effect where women's exclusion from early promotions restricts their trajectory toward senior leadership roles. In the NCS context, this "broken rung" is further reinforced by the Service's hierarchical and male-dominated structure, where leadership succession largely favors men.

Furthermore, the study's results therefore highlight a critical policy and institutional gap: despite Nigeria's commitment to gender equality through frameworks such as the National Gender Policy (2021–2026) and international conventions like CEDAW, these commitments have yet to translate into equitable outcomes in paramilitary institutions. The NCS remains emblematic of this gap, no woman has ever served as Comptroller-General since its establishment, and only a handful occupy senior command roles (NCS, 2024). The implication is that gender inequality in promotion not only undermines women's career progression but also deprives the organization of diverse leadership perspectives that could enhance innovation, efficiency, and integrity. Thus, this study provides empirical confirmation that dismantling the "glass ceiling" in the NCS is a prerequisite for achieving genuine gender inclusion and institutional effectiveness. Transparent, merit-based promotion procedures supported by mentorship, capacity building, and leadership development for women are essential to bridge the current gap.

5.1 CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between gender inequality in promotion and women's career progression within the Nigerian Customs Service, focusing on the Sokoto/Zamfara Command. The findings revealed a strong and statistically significant negative relationship, indicating that pervasive gender bias in promotion practices severely limits women's upward mobility. Despite female officers demonstrating competence, diligence, and professional commitment, their advancement to senior or strategic leadership levels remains constrained by entrenched institutional norms and opaque promotion systems. Anchored on the Glass Ceiling Theory, the study concludes that women in the NCS encounter structural and cultural impediments that restrict their access to higher ranks. These barriers manifest not through lack of merit but through discriminatory perceptions of leadership, gender stereotyping, and institutional practices that favor men in decision-making and promotion processes.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that;

- The Nigerian Customs Service (NCS), through its Headquarters, should urgently reform its promotion system by establishing a Gender Equity and Promotion Review Committee (GEPRC) to ensure transparency, fairness, and merit-based advancement. This committee should conduct a comprehensive gender audit of past promotion exercises, develop clear and objective promotion criteria, and ensure that promotion boards are gender-balanced and monitored by independent observers from the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs or the Federal Character Commission to minimize bias.
- Furthermore, the Federal Ministry of Finance, as the supervisory body, should enforce compliance by integrating gender equity benchmarks into the NCS's annual performance evaluations and linking compliance with institutional rewards or sanctions where necessary.
- In addition, the Ministry of Women Affairs should collaborate with the NCS to implement targeted capacity-building initiatives, including mentorship and leadership development programs such as a *Women in Customs Leadership Initiative (WICLI)* to enhance female officers' preparedness for higher responsibilities.
- Likewise, the National Assembly, through its committees on public service and gender affairs, should strengthen legislative oversight by mandating at least 35% female representation in promotion and appointment boards to institutionalize fairness. Finally, the Training and Development Department of the NCS should promote a gender-sensitive organizational culture through continuous awareness programs, anti-bias training, and confidential reporting mechanisms to address discrimination. Collectively, these measures will help dismantle structural barriers, promote inclusive career advancement, and ensure that competence rather than gender determines progression within the Nigerian Customs Service.

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